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Strona | 271

STUDY OF FACTORS AFFECTING MIGRATION ATTRACTIVENESS

Introduction

Modern dynamic conditions of the global economic environment require countries and regions to build and implement an effective geo-economic strategy, an integral part of which is the management of human resources and their migration. Today, migration is becoming more widespread, and at the same time, forced migration is also increasing. The reasons for this are economic and social problems, the aggravation of military-political conflicts, the situation surrounding Covid 19, and climate change. The socio-economic significance of migration is manifested in helping to overcome population poverty – the amount of remittances from migrants to their countries of origin increases annually, and the majority of them are sent to low- and middle-income countries.

Population migration is determined primarily by economic and social reasons. Among them, regional labor markets are the most important when assessing the attractiveness of countries. It is they who form the directions of migration flows and are peculiar regulators of the intensity of territorial movements. Therefore, when studying migration processes, it is advisable to study the factors that have the most significant impact on migration attractiveness.

Literature review

Key scientific developments in the field of studying human resource migration processes are represented by many scientific works, in particular: Savoskul³ proposed the concept of territorial migration systems, in which he considers international population migrations as a complex phenomenon of specific regional, social and temporal dimensions with

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³ Savoskul M. S. Territorial systems of the international migrations of population. Vestnik Moskovskogo Universiteta, Seriya 5: Geografiya, 2015-January(6), 11-18.

specific development trends. Grzegorzcyk proved that the socio-spatial aspect of cities in the era of globalization acquired a new dimension. Potudanskaya et al⁴ substantiated the spheres of regulation of labor migration, the essence of which is to ensure a decent standard of living of the population in the region and to create an appropriate migration infrastructure. Nizamutdinov & Malaev⁵ consider migration through three main dimensions: finance, production and the social sphere. Based on them, factors of direct and indirect effect on the migratory attractiveness of the region are formed. Lee⁶ suggests considering migration attractiveness through the prism of the concept of sustainable development, as international competition in various areas is growing, in particular: tourism (Kinash et al⁷), manufacturing (Cherchata et al⁸), education. Luzina & Ignatova proposed a model for assessing the attractiveness of jobs based on objective indicators of regional development and identified the main reasons for inefficient use of labor resources. Fajfrová et al in their study offer different options for reducing migration flows. One proposal is the "mass migration process" (MMP), a conservative system of particles on INZd. Drobne investigated migration processes in Slovenia and concluded that the country's economic decline is a catalyst for migration, the poorer the population, the higher the migration of human resources from this country. Bertoli et al⁹ say that migration depends not only on their relative attractiveness, but also on alternative destinations. Drobne & Bogataj proved that the higher the population aging index, the higher the migration attractiveness index of the country. Dotti et al say that universities are a source of selective migration processes and possibly different directions of development, increasing the opportunities of economically dynamic regions to attract bright people from lagging regions. KurushinaV & Druzhinina suggested

⁴ Potudanskaya V. F., Borovskikh N. V., & Kipervar E. A. Labor migration in the region: Assessment, forecasting, approaches to management. *Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 2018 (Special Issue 3), 2413-6670.

⁵ Nizamutdinov I. K., & Malaev V. V. The economic development of the regions and the migration. *Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 2018 (Special Issue 5), 296-299.

⁶ Lee K. The conceptualization of country attractiveness: A review of research. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 82(4), 807-826.

⁷ Kinash I. P., Arkhypova L. M., Polyanska A. S., Dzoba O. G., Andrusiv U. Y., & Iuras I. I. Economic evaluation of tourism infrastructure development in Ukraine. Paper presented at the IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 2019. 477(1).

⁸ Cherchata A., Popovychenko I., Andrusiv U., Simkiv L., Kliukha O & Horai O. A methodology for analysis and assessment of business processes of Ukrainian enterprises. *Management Science Letters*, 10(3), 2020. 631-640.

⁹ Bertoli S., & Fernández-Huertas Moraga J. Multilateral resistance to migration. *Journal of Development Economics*, 102, 2013. 79-100.

looking at migration by modeling the migration growth rate and assessing changes in priorities among migrants according to the concepts of economic, sustainable and inclusive development. Čábelková et al¹⁰ conducted an analysis of the relationship between job satisfaction, socio-demographic characteristics of employees and workplace relations using the example of the Czech Republic. Zamyatina et al prove that the migration phenomenon of Belgorod is the result of a number of factors, including the proximity of Ukraine to northern migrants from relatives in this country, a high level of urban development in the city itself, subsidized house purchase programs, etc.

Andrusiv et al¹¹ in their work say that the higher the level of development of the region, the more attractive it is for migrants. Ievdokymov et al¹² claim that successful and effective management of labor resources is possible only if the objects of management are subject to measurement, that is, subject to not only qualitative, but also quantitative assessment.

However, Yevdokimov et al add that the adoption of the circular economy concept can have a significant impact on the human resource management system. Shymanska et al¹³ in their work formed the main economic factors of migration from Ukraine, which included: high level of corruption in the country, high unemployment, corrupt and ineffective system of judicial protection, high level of inflation, high level of taxation of labor income and low wages.

Despite the large number of scientists who have studied migration issues, there is no unequivocal hypothesis of migration attractiveness, so the question of the migration attractiveness model is relevant.

The purpose of the article is to study the factors affecting migration processes in Ukraine and build a model of migration attractiveness.

Results

In the conditions of the dynamic global economic environment, the

¹⁰ Čábelková I., Kiseleva L., & Strielkowski W. Study of influence of socio-demographic characteristics of workers on job satisfaction (the case of the Czech Republic). *Human Ecology (Russian Federation)*, 2015(4), 39-46.

¹¹ Andrusiv U., Simkiv L., Dovgal O., Demchuk N., Potryvaieva N., Cherchata A., Popadynets I., Tkachenko G., Serhieieva O & Sydor H. Analysis of economic development of Ukraine regions based on taxonomy method. *Management Science Letters*, 10(3), 2020. 515-522.

¹² Ievdokymov V., Oliinyk O., Grytsyshen D., Ksendzuk V., & Nord G. The new geological epoch, "anthropocene," as a result of human economic activity. *Comparative Economic Research*, 21(3), 2018. 131-149.

¹³ Shymanska K. V., Kurylo M., Karmaza O., & Timchenko G. Determinants of migration motives as a precondition for the migration flows formation. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 15(3), 2017. 1-13.

problems of international migration of human resources are relevant and placed on the agenda of the world community, because the mobility of human resources affects the state of socio-economic development of the population, ecological well-being of territories, and political stability.

For a more detailed analysis, we will form indicators by groups of factors that, in our opinion, have the most significant impact on migration attractiveness:

- by groups of economic factors;
- by groups of socio-demographic factors;
- by groups of political and security factors;
- by groups of linguistic and cultural factors;
- by groups of ecological and natural factors.

For a more detailed analysis, we will form groups of factors and their indicators in Table 1.

Table 1 – Groups of factors and their indicators for the formation of the migration attractiveness model

Factors	Indicators
D_E – economic factors of migration attractiveness	<p>K_{Π} : K_{pi6} – unemployment rate (E1.1), $K_{\text{cnpс}}$ – labor demand structure (E1.2), $K_{\text{poп}}$ – salary level (E1.3), $K_{\text{poтд}}$ – the level of labor income taxation (E1.4);</p> <p>K_{B6} : $K_{\text{лвз6}}$ – indicators of ease of opening and closing a business (E2.1), $K_{\text{poпд}}$ – the level of business income taxation (E2.2);</p> <p>K_{3M} : K_{pi} – inflation rate (E3.1), $K_{\text{iфзз}}$ – indicator of existing forms of savings (E3.2), $K_{\text{н6с}}$ – an indicator of the reliability of the banking system (E3.3), $K_{\text{poм}}$ – an indicator of the level of property taxation (E3.4);</p> <p>$K_{\text{иH}}$: $K_{\text{дзз}}$ – indicator of access to means of communication (E4.1), $K_{\text{ppктс}}$ – an indicator of the development and diversity of transport communication channels (E4.2), $K_{\text{pшг}}$ – indicator of the road industry development (E4.3);</p> <p>$K_{\text{зеп}}$: $K_{\text{сзп}}$ – indicator of the labor rights protection system (E5.1), $K_{\text{сзпа}}$ – system of shareholders' rights protection (E5.2), K_{copno} – indicator of the system of appealing decisions of tax authorities (E5.3).</p>
D_S – socio-demographic factors of migration attractiveness	<p>$K_{\text{д}}$: $K_{\text{шрн}}$ – population density indicator (S1.1), $K_{\text{свсн}}$ – indicator of the sex-age composition of the population (S1.2);</p>

	<p>$K_{дсб}$: $K_{рссс}$ – indicator of the social insurance system development (S2.1), $K_{рсо}$ – an indicator of the education system development (S2.2), $K_{рсоз}$ – an indicator of the health care system development (S2.3);</p> <p>$K_{зсдп}$: $K_{сзпдп}$ – indicator of the system of the rights of people with disabilities protection (S3.1), $K_{сзбгд}$ – determinant of the system of protection against gender discrimination (S3.2), $K_{сзпс}$ – indicator of the consumer rights protection system (S3.3).</p>
D_P – a political and security indicator of migration attractiveness	<p>$K_{пд}$ – political and ideological determinants (includes the Communist Party - the political regime in the country (P1.1), $K_{ркк}$ – level of corruption in the country (P1.2), $K_{рпд}$ – the presence of political movements that involve intolerance towards certain categories of the population (P1.3));</p> <p>$K_{бб}$ – military and security determinants (incl $K_{зкпс}$ – the state's participation in armed conflicts and the post-conflict state of the state's territory (P2.1), $K_{всзс}$ – requirements of compulsory service in the armed forces (P2.2);</p> <p>$K_{зпс}$ – indicator of civil rights and freedoms protection (incl $K_{сзтз}$ – system of protection against terrorist threats (P3.1), $K_{зпдм}$ – a system of protection against politically motivated persecution (P3.2), $K_{сзс}$ – system of judicial protection (P3.3).</p>
D_L – linguistic and cultural factors of migration attractiveness	<p>$K_{ме}$ – linguistic and ethnic indicator (L1); $K_{рк}$ – religious and cultural indicator (L2); $K_{зпс}$ – indicator of civil rights and freedoms protection (L3)</p>
D_N – ecological and natural factors of migration attractiveness	<p>$K_{пк}$: $K_{пкы}$ - natural and climatic conditions (N1.1), $K_{екп}$ – risks of extreme climatic events (N1.2);</p> <p>K_e : $K_{сзнс}$ – degree of environmental pollution (N2.1), $K_{дчвх}$ – access to clean drinking water and environmentally friendly food (N2.2);</p> <p>$K_{зекп}$: $K_{зпбнс}$ – protection of rights to a safe environment (N3.1), $K_{свзнс}$ – system of responsibility for environmental pollution (N3.2).</p>

Let's consider in more detail the impact of each group of factors on the resulting indicator:

modeling the influence of economic determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness. In general, we consider it appropriate to present the model of the influence of economic determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness in the following formalized form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 D_E = \alpha_1 \times K_n + \alpha_2 \times K_{вб} + \alpha_3 \times K_{зм} + \alpha_4 \times K_{ін} + \alpha_5 \times K_{зеп} \\
 K_n \langle K_{рб}, K_{спрс}, K_{роп}, K_{ротд} \rangle \\
 K_{вб} \langle K_{лвзб}, K_{ропд} \rangle \\
 K_{зм} \langle K_{рі}, K_{іфзз}, K_{нбс}, K_{ром} \rangle \\
 K_{ін} \langle K_{дзз}, K_{ррктс}, K_{ршг} \rangle \\
 K_{зеп} \langle K_{сзтп}, K_{сзпа}, K_{сорпо} \rangle \\
 \text{at the same time:} \\
 \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + \alpha_5 = 1
 \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where D_E – economic determinants of migration attractiveness;

K_n – determinants of employment;

$K_{вб}$ – determinants of doing business;

$K_{зм}$ – determinants of property preservation\$

$K_{ін}$ – determinants of infrastructure conditions\$

$K_{зеп}$ – детермінанти захисту економічних прав.

- modeling the influence of socio-demographic determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness. Socio-demographic indicators are no less important than economic indicators, because they highlight the nature of relationships in society and the population's access to public goods, which largely determines the standard of living. In general, we consider it appropriate to present the model of the influence of socio-demographic determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness in the following formalized form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 D_S = \alpha_1 \times K_{\partial} + \alpha_2 \times K_{дсб} + \alpha_3 \times K_{зсдп} \\
 K_{\partial} \langle K_{щрн}, K_{свсн} \rangle \\
 K_{дсб} \langle K_{рссс}, K_{рсо}, K_{рсоз} \rangle \\
 K_{зсдп} \langle K_{зплі}, K_{згд}, K_{кятп} \rangle \\
 \text{at the same time:} \\
 \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 1
 \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

where D_S – socio-demographic indicator of migration attractiveness;

K_{∂} – demographic determinants;

$K_{дсб}$ – determinants of access to public goods;

$K_{зсдп}$ – determinants of socio-demographic rights protection system.

modeling the influence of political and security determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness. In the basic formulation, the recommended model for assessing migration attractiveness based on political and security determinants takes into account both the relevant factors of the country's environment and institutional factors and has the form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_P = \alpha_1 \times K_{\text{пi}} + \alpha_2 \times K_{\text{Б6}} + \alpha_3 \times K_{\text{ЗГПc}} \\ K_{\text{пi}} \langle K_{\text{пРк}}, K_{\text{РКк}}, K_{\text{РПН}} \rangle \\ K_{\text{Б6}} \langle K_{\text{ЗКПc}}, K_{\text{Вoc3c}} \rangle \\ K_{\text{ЗГПc}} \langle K_{\text{c3т3}}, K_{\text{ЗППМ}}, K_{\text{cc3}} \rangle \\ \text{at the same time:} \\ \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where D_P – a political and security indicator of migration attractiveness.

- modeling the influence of linguistic and cultural determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness. It is more difficult to parameterize the influence of linguistic and cultural determinants due to their certain subjectivity. However, in this case, we suggest using the approach not so much of the proximity of the cultural environment for the migrant, but the existence of such an institutional environment that excludes discrimination on ethnic, racial, cultural, religious and other grounds, supports multiculturalism and provides support for the self-identification of individuals. This approach determined the selection of relevant information sources for the calculation of indicators. In general, we consider it appropriate to present the model of linguistic and cultural determinants influence on the indicator of migration attractiveness in the following formalized form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_L = \alpha_1 \times K_{\text{Me}} + \alpha_2 \times K_{\text{Рк}} + \alpha_3 \times K_{\text{ЗГПc}} \\ \text{at the same time:} \\ \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

where D_L – linguistic and cultural indicator of migration attractiveness.

- modeling the influence of ecological and natural determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness. Ecological and natural factors are also difficult to measure, based on the uniqueness of natural and climatic conditions of each country, its resource potential. In general, we consider it appropriate to present the model of the influence of ecological and natural determinants on the indicator of migration attractiveness in the following formalized form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_N = \alpha_1 \times K_{\text{пк}} + \alpha_2 \times K_e + \alpha_3 \times K_{\text{Зекп}} \\ K_{\text{пк}} \langle K_{\text{пкУ}}, K_{\text{екп}} \rangle \\ K_e \langle K_{\text{c3нc}}, K_{\text{дчвх}} \rangle \\ K_{\text{Зекп}} \langle K_{\text{зпбнc}}, K_{\text{св3нc}} \rangle \\ \text{at the same time:} \\ \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

where D_N – ecological and natural indicator of migration attractiveness;

$K_{\text{нк}}$ – natural and climatic determinants;

K_e – environmental determinants;

$K_{зекп}$ – determinants of environmental rights protection.

At the same time, taking into account the expediency of measuring the influence of each group of indicators of the formation of the migration motive on migration attractiveness, we justified and built a model of an integral indicator, which is a weighted average sum of synthetic indicators aggregated by groups of economic (E), socio-demographic (S), political security (P), linguistic and cultural (L) and ecological and natural (N) normalized indicators that demonstrate the determinants of the formation of the migration motive. Thus, in the most generalized representation, the migration attractiveness model has sums of synthetic indicators aggregated by groups of determinants (formula 6):

$$I_{migr} = \gamma_1 D_E + \gamma_2 D_S + \gamma_3 D_P + \gamma_4 D_L + \gamma_5 D_N \quad (6)$$

where D_E, D_S, D_P, D_L, D_N – indicators of migration attractiveness by groups of economic, socio-demographic, political-security, linguistic-cultural and ecological-natural determinants, respectively;

γ – the weight factor of the group of determinants.

Розрахунок D_E, D_S, D_P, D_L, D_N according to the following formulas::

$$D_E = \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i K_{E_k} \quad D_S = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i K_{S_k} \quad D_P = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i K_{P_k} \quad (7)$$

$$D_L = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i K_{L_k} \quad D_N = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i K_{N_k} \quad (8)$$

where i – the number of subgroups of determinants in the group (5 – for economic, 3 – for other groups);

k – the number of determinants in the subgroup, α is the weight coefficient of the subgroup of determinants;

K_E, K_S, K_P, K_L, K_N – indicators of migration attractiveness are determined by subgroups of the above-mentioned groups of determinants.

Thus, an economic-mathematical model of migration attractiveness assessment was formed in a general form and the components of this model were specified in the form of linear equations, with the definition of the information base for their calculation. In order to take into account the personal importance of certain determinants identified for research, it is advisable to introduce correction coefficients into the model, the values of which should be determined by applying the expert survey method. In particular, the issue of point assessment of the importance of determinants for the formation of personal migration motives should be submitted to the expert survey. At the same time, it is necessary to establish not only the degree of influence of each group of determinants on the resulting indicator, but also each subgroup on the group and each determinant on the subgroup. Therefore, it is suggested to calculate the weighting factors α using the following formulas:

1) Weight coefficients of each determinant:

$$\beta_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Bal_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^p Bal_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

where n – the number of respondents;

p – the number of determinants in the subgroup;

Bal_i – the number of points given to each determinant by those surveyed;

Bal_{ij} – the number of points in the i -th interviewee for the j -th determinant.

2) Coefficients of each subgroup of determinants:

$$\alpha_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^p Bal_{ij}}{\sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^p Bal_{ijl}} \quad (10)$$

where m – the number of subgroups of determinants in one group of determinants;

Bal_{ij} – the number of points in the i -th respondent for the j -th determinant of the subgroup of determinants l .

3) Coefficients of groups of determinants:

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^p Bal_{ijl}}{P} \quad (11)$$

where P – the sum of all point estimates of all determinants.

Thus, the formalization of the migration attractiveness indicators according to the substantiated and developed model is adaptive from the point of view of the possibility of expanding the panel of used indicators, as well as choosing the base for calculating weighting factors. In particular, we believe that this economic-mathematical model can be applied to determine the migration attractiveness of countries for certain sex-age and educational-professional groups of migrants, and the use of the survey method allows to separate these groups into samples, using other indicators for selection.

In general, when analyzing the importance of determinants for the formation of migration motives, a number of indicators were used to assess the importance (gradation) of each determinant:

- 1) the average value of the determinant in points;
- 2) average rank for each determinant;
- 3) the frequency of maximum possible ratings (100 points) given by experts to each determinant;
- 4) the average weight of each determinant (normalized assessment).

Let's consider the indicated indicators in more detail:

- 1) The average value of the determinant in points. With the formula provided by B.E. Hrabovetsky transformed:

$$M_j = \sum_{l=1}^5 \delta_l \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m C_{ij}}{m_j} \quad (12)$$

$$\delta_l = \frac{k_l \times \omega_{il}}{\sum_{l=1}^5 k_l \times \omega_{il}}, \quad (13)$$

where k_l – the number of experts in the l -th group;
 ω_{il} – coefficient of awareness of the j -th expert y l -th group;
 $\delta_l - \delta_l$ is the weighting factor of the l th group.

In particular, this indicator (M_j) is defined as the weighted average of the array of experts' assessments of the j -th determinant and can take values from 0 to 100, based on the experts' individual assessment of the importance of the determinant for the formation of their personal migration motives. In this regard, the importance of the determinant is higher, the greater the value of M_j . According to this indicator, the determinants, which are characterized by the highest average value of the assessment, have been determined. These include: low and/or unsatisfactory level of remuneration (77.50); high level of corruption in the country (75.33); corrupt and/or inefficient judicial protection system (73.15); the state's participation in armed conflicts and the post-conflict state of the state's territory (70,43); high level of unemployment (70.33).

2) Average rank for each determinant. This indicator is calculated based on the indicator of the sum of the ranks of the j -th determinant according to the formula:

$$\bar{S}_j = \sum_{l=1}^5 \delta_l \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m C_{ij}}{m_j} = \sum_{l=1}^5 \delta_l \times \frac{S_j}{m} \quad (14)$$

In particular, based on the results of the calculation of this indicator, the determinants characterized by the smallest values were selected. These include: low and/or unsatisfactory level of remuneration (10.0); high level of corruption in the country (10.8); corrupt and/or inefficient judicial protection system (10.9); high level of unemployment (12.6); the state's participation in armed conflicts and the post-conflict state of the state's territory (12,7).

3) The frequency of maximum possible ratings (100 points) given by experts to each determinant. This indicator is calculated according to the formula:

$$K_{100j} = \sum_{l=1}^5 \delta_l \times \frac{m_{100j}}{m_j} \quad (15)$$

According to the results of the evaluation of this indicator, the determinants were determined, to which the experts gave the largest possible number of evaluations (100 points): high level of corruption in

the country (0.5043); low and/or unsatisfactory level of remuneration (0.5000); corrupt and/or inefficient judicial protection system (0.4739); the state's participation in armed conflicts and the post-conflict state of the state's territory (0.4739); the existence of terrorist threats and/or a low level of protection against them (0.3609). At the same time, the indicator of the frequency of providing the maximum possible ratings, according to Grabovetskyi (2010), "refers to additional indicators of assessing the relative importance of factors and characterizes it from the point of view of the number of maximum ratings of 100 points assigned to it. Preference for one or another factor should be given, first of all, depending on the average values of the rank or points. And only under different conditions, the factor can be considered the most important for the maximum value of K_{100j} ".

4) Grabovetskyi (2010) in addition to absolute and average values, suggests calculating the relative importance of determinants, for example, the average weight indicator. Taking into account the above, the average weight of each determinant (normalized score) is calculated according to the formula transformed by us:

$$W_j = \sum_{l=1}^5 \delta_l \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m W_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m W_{ij}}; \quad W_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n C_{ij}}, \quad (16)$$

where W_{ij} – weight (normalized assessment) given by the i th expert to the j th determinant W_j is the total weight given by experts to the j th determinant.

Based on the results of determining the normalized assessment, a matrix of the relative value of the indicators was compiled. This made it possible to single out the prevailing indicators, the impact of which on the formation of migration motives was determined to be the most significant.

Table 2 - Summary results of aggregated expert assessments of the importance of indicators of the formation of migration motives

Code indicator	Arithmetic mean value of of the indicator significance assessment (\overline{M}_j)	The average rank of the indicator (\overline{S}_j)	The frequency of maximum possible evaluations (K_{100j})	Average weight (normalized score) (W_j)
1	2	3	4	5
E1.3	77,50	10,0	0,5000	0,04250
P1.2	75,33	10,8	0,5043	0,04025
E1.1	70,33	12,6	0,3261	0,03865

P3.3	73,15	10,9	0,4739	0,03676
P2.1	70,43	12,7	0,4739	0,03633
E2.1	64,02	13,1	0,2652	0,03259
E1.4	62,83	14,3	0,2478	0,03251
E2.2	60,98	15,4	0,2565	0,03185
N3.1	62,50	14,8	0,3174	0,03133
E3.1	58,70	16,5	0,2043	0,03058
N3.2	61,74	14,9	0,2826	0,02965
S2.3	59,24	15,7	0,2348	0,02869
P3.1	60,98	15,6	0,3609	0,02842
E1.2	51,30	19,3	0,1565	0,02808
S3.3	58,80	16,2	0,2826	0,02778
E4.3	54,78	17,2	0,1826	0,02632
E3.4	52,72	18,6	0,1174	0,02605
P1.3	55,11	17,3	0,2087	0,02515
E3.2	52,61	18,1	0,1913	0,02502
E3.3	51,20	18,5	0,1870	0,02479
S2.2	49,13	19,6	0,1348	0,02351
P1.1	50,43	19,2	0,1565	0,02316
E5.3	49,24	19,2	0,1609	0,02207
P3.2	46,74	20,3	0,1739	0,02076
S3.1	45,54	22,1	0,1435	0,02053
P2.2	46,41	21,2	0,2130	0,02024
S2.1	43,26	23,1	0,1087	0,01925
L2	45,33	21,7	0,2174	0,01881
N1.1	41,63	23,0	0,1174	0,01768
E5.1	39,78	23,7	0,0957	0,01761
E5.2	40,43	23,8	0,0870	0,01733
S1.2	36,74	24,2	0,0609	0,01714
S3.2	38,48	23,8	0,0652	0,01691
E4.2	38,15	24,0	0,1000	0,01662
N2.2	37,61	24,0	0,1391	0,01659
L3	40,98	23,6	0,1870	0,01621
L1	39,78	24,4	0,1870	0,01597
N2.1	35,76	25,9	0,0826	0,01528
E4.1	32,93	25,4	0,1000	0,01442
N1.2	32,72	26,5	0,1043	0,01353
S1.1	29,35	27,4	0,0696	0,01308

Based on the data in Table 2, which summarizes individual expert assessments of the importance of indicators for the formation of migration motives, the indicators with the highest average weight are determined:

- low and/or unsatisfactory level of remuneration (E1.3);
- high level of corruption in the country (P1.2);

- high level of unemployment (E1.1);
- corrupt and/or ineffective judicial protection system (P3.3);
- the existence of terrorist threats and/or a low level of protection against them (P2.1).

Other indicators that are included in the 25% most important (based on the indicator of the upper quartile) include:

- ease of opening and closing a business (E2.1);
- level of taxation of labor income (E1.4);
- level of taxation of business income (E2.2);
- protection of rights to a safe environment (N3.1);
- inflation rate (E3.1);
- the system of responsibility for environmental pollution (N3.2).

Conclusions

A group of factors was formed in terms of economic, socio-demographic, political-security, linguistic-cultural and ecological-natural indicators, which demonstrate the indicators of the formation of the migration motive. The impact of each group of indicators on the resulting indicator is considered and demonstrated. The developed model for assessing the migration attractiveness of the country based on certain factors. In this case, in contrast to the economic-mathematical model given above, the resulting indicator is the number of migrants from the country, for forecasting of which, in fact, the integrated indicator of migration attractiveness is intended.

The results of the study allow us to talk about the expediency of implementing the specified model in the methodology of research on the level of migration attractiveness for state authorities, using it in the implementation of analytical studies by international and regional organizations, as well as non-governmental public organizations for the purpose of ranking the countries of the world according to the level of migration attractiveness and in the context of the formation of of «attraction-repulsion» factors that determine the vectors of migration flows.

Abstract: The author's vision of the list of factors that should be introduced into the economic-mathematical model of migration attractiveness is formed. The factors are formed according to the indicators of the formation of the migration motive, namely: economic, socio-demographic, political-security, linguistic-cultural and ecological-natural. A mathematical model for assessing migration attractiveness is proposed to ensure the possibility of forecasting future migration flows. It was found that the higher the level of migration attractiveness of the country, the weaker is the migration motive of the individual. Based on the nature of the relationship between migration motives and migration attractiveness, a specification of empirical data for calculating migration attractiveness was formed and the influence of determinants on the resulting indicator was characterized. A linear model was chosen to parameterize migration attractiveness. At the same time, taking into account the expediency of measuring the influence of each group of indicators of the formation of the migration motive on migration attractiveness, we justified and built a model of an integral indicator, which is a weighted average sum of synthetic indicators aggregated by groups of economic (E), socio-demographic (S), political security (P), linguistic and cultural (L) and ecological and natural (N) normalized indicators, which demonstrate the indicators of the formation of the migration motive.

Keywords: factors, migration, migration processes, migration attractiveness.

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